

Ocular Complications of Severe VKC in Gaya District

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this study was to assess the ocular complications and visual loss among patients with severe VKC.

Method: Four hundred patients with VKC seen at ANMMCH, Gaya. This was a retrospective non-comparative observational study conducted between 1st January 2021 to 31st December 2021.

Results: Out of 400 patients, 300 were male and 100 were females. The majority of the patients were in 5-9 age group (167) followed by 135 in 10-14 age groups.

Conclusion: Severe VKC in developing countries including Yemen is a potentially blinding disease. Visual loss may be due to keratoconus and corneal scars, as well as complications of the unsupervised use of topically administered corticosteroids.

Keywords: Cataract, Glaucoma, Keratoconus, Visual impairment, Vernal keratoconjunctivitis.

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Introduction

The eye is a frequent target of inflammation in both local and systemic allergic reactions. The vast majority of ocular allergy affects the conjunctiva. Vernal keratoconjunctivitis (VKC) is a severe form of ocular allergic conjunctivitis causing disturbance of normal activities at school or work due to severe itching, grittiness, foreign body sensation, difficulty in opening the eyelids, photophobia and copious mucous discharge. [1]

VKC is a potentially severe, chronic, allergic condition, causing bilateral recurrent inflammatory disorder of the conjunctiva and cornea. Typically occurs in males before the age of 10 in 80% of cases, it lasts 2–10 years, and it usually

resolves during puberty. Males have an earlier presentation of symptoms than females and the male to female ratio decreases with age. [2]

Keratoconjunctivitis define as an inflammatory condition in which both cornea and conjunctiva is included. There are five category of ocular allergy: Seasonal allergic conjunctivities, perennial allergic conjunctivities, Vernal kerratoconjunctivities (VKC), Atopic kerratoconjunctivities (AKC), Perennial keratoconjunctivities (PKC)and giant papillary conjunctivities(GPC). [6] VKC is stand for Vernal keratoconjunctivitis. It is mostly found in pediatric age group. It is chronic, bilateral, inflammatory and allergic disorder. [3] It mainly found in

first decade of life. 90% percent Case resolved till the age of puberty with good prognosis, only 10 percent case affect the eye health. [4] VKC is symptomatic allergic form, Which create disturbance in day to day life such as irritation not able to open eyes, foreign body sensation, photophobia, watering, itching, discharge and rubbing. The prevalence of VKC is hot and dry area such as Mediterranean basin, the Middle East, Africa and the Indian subcontinent). It is relatively unusual in most of North America and Western Europe (Bremond-Gignac et al., 2008). It affects the conjunctival part such as palpebral, bulbar, limbal and also cornea. [5] The diagnosis depends upon the sign and symptom, but in severe cases conjunctival scarring is best method to diagnosed VKC because in scarring we found out the infiltration of eosinophils. [2]

VKC is more prevalent in hot and dry areas (Mediterranean basin, the Middle East, Africa and the Indian subcontinent). It is relatively unusual in most of North America and Western Europe. [7] Risk factors include age, underlying atopic predisposition, extent of allergen exposure and individual immune response to antigenic stimulation. There is a significant history of other atopic manifestations such as eczema or asthma in patients with VKC. [8,9]

A family history of atopy is found in these patients. Three types of VKC are recognized. Limbal type (fine papillae with circumferential gelatinous limbal infiltration and Horner-Trantas dots); the palpebral type (giant papillae of >1 mm in diameter on the superior tarsal conjunctiva) and a mixed type. These features leave no doubt as to the diagnosis

of VKC. The reasons underlying the development of the various types of VKC in these patients are not understood. The signs include papillary response of the conjunctiva, principally of the limbus or upper tarsus; thick, abundant andropy mucus; Trantas dots and "cobblestone papillae". Keratitis (which occurs in up to 50% of cases) [10] and shield ulcers are sight-threatening complications. There is an association of Keratoconus in VKC patients. [11]

The objective of this study was to assess the ocular complications and visual loss among patients with severe VKC.

Materials And Methods

Four hundred patients with VKC seen at ANMMCH, Gaya. This was a retrospective non-comparative observational study conducted between 1st January 2021 to 31st December 2021. Visual activity was measured with the standard snellen visual acuity chart and for groups of children under 5 years of age Key pictures were used, Visual impairment was assessed by means of WHO criteria for visual disabilities. Cases with severe VKC that developed ocular complications leading to blindness and severe visual impairment were analysed.

The majority of VKC patients were male with male: female ratio of 3:1. A total of 60(15%) patients (45 boys and 15 girls) had severe VKC.

The ocular findings among 18 patients with severe VKC that lead to blindness and severe visual impairment included Keratoconus (6), steroid induced cataract (5), Central corneal scar (4) and steroid induced glaucoma (3). Two of the keratoconus cases developed acute hydrops.

60 patients developed severe VKC

$V_n > 6/24 = 24(40\%)$

$V_n = 6/60 - 6h/24 = 18(30\%)$

$V_n = 3/60 - 6/6 = 12(20\%)$

$V_n < 3/60 = 6(10\%)$

Results

Table 1: Demographic details

Age	Male	Female	Total
0-4	23	6	29
5-9	120	47	167
10-14	101	34	135
15-19	52	10	62
>20	4	3	7
Total	300	100	400

Out of 400 patients, 300 were male and 100 were females. Majority of the patients were in 5-9 age group (167) followed by 135 in 10-14 age groups.

Table 2

	Total	Palpebral	Limbal	Mixed	Age of onset (In years)
Male	300	117(39.2%)	134(44.6%)	49(16.3%)	6.5±5(1-24)
Female	100	18(18.1%)	69(58.9%)	23(23%)	7.5±5(1-25)
Total	400	135(33.75%)	193(48.25%)	72(18%)	7±5(1-25)

Discussion

Allergic eye diseases including vernal keratoconjunctivitis (VKC) are common diseases in the Mediterranean region including Yemen. [12] In Nigeria, VKC was identified as the most common conjunctival disease in children seen in hospital. [13] A study done by Farouk et al. (2005) in Kuwait University Hospital in Sana'a, Yemen showed that allergic eye diseases is the second most common diagnosis in the eye clinics after refractive errors. [14]

Majority of cases with VKC examined in this study were younger than 10 years while still the disease persists to the adult age in a number of patients after the age of 20 years. Majority of cases were males (75.9%) with male to female ratio of 3.1:1 and that is similar to studies from Italy and Thailand. [12,15,16]

Diagnosis of VKC was based on the patient's history and the presence of typical clinical signs and symptoms. The most common clinical type of VKC in this study was the limbal type followed by the palpebral type and is the same as reported in other studies. [12,15]

The ocular complications leading to blindness and severe visual impairment affected 20 patients (4.6%) and that is similar compared to studies. [7] In a study by Tabbara in Saudi Arabia, 21% had a BSCVA of 20/200 or less due to steroid-induced cataract, steroid-induced glaucoma, central corneal scars, irregular astigmatism and keratoconus. [17]

Therapy for mild VKC includes preservative-free artificial tears, cold compresses and antihistamines. Treatment in severe cases of VKC is still problematic due to frequent exacerbations. Topical corticosteroids are usually given only for a short period of time to avoid the risk of side effects including glaucoma, cataract and infection. [9] Unfortunately patients and their relatives keep seeing more than one doctor looking for cure from the

disease and this leads to the prolonged unsupervised use of steroid drops and increasing the risk of complications. Cyclosporine drops have good effect in VKC cases with fewer side effects compared to corticosteroids but unfortunately it is not available in Yemen. [18] A close ophthalmological supervision with controlled discontinuous treatment according to the disease severity is essential to avoid self-prescription and misuse of steroid drops. [19]

Limitations of this study are: There were no immunological diagnostic tests done to this group of patients because of limitations in the facilities available in Yemen. History of other associated allergic diseases and family history of allergic diseases were not documented in this study. Also, patients were not grouped to those who come from desert areas or the mountains to study the differences in presentations and ocular complications.

Conclusion

VKC is quite a common disease in the parts of Bihar (Gaya district) and severe form of VKC is a potentially blinding disease. Visual loss may be due to keratoconus and corneal scar as well as complications of the unsupervised use of topically administered steroids.

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